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**TRADITIONAL VEGETABLES AS NATURAL
ANTIDIABETIC CANDIDATES: A REVIEW OF
PHYTOCHEMICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL
EVIDENCE**

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ABSTRACT: Herbal medicine is being researched for its potential to help control blood sugar levels in diabetes, offering alternative treatment options. Diabetes mellitus is a chronic condition where the body struggles to regulate blood sugar due to issues with insulin production or function, leading to high blood glucose levels. Conventional therapies often produce adverse effects, prompting the search for natural alternatives with better safety profiles. Traditional vegetables, consumed globally, have been recognized not only as nutritious foods but also as sources of bioactive compounds with antidiabetic potential. Phytochemicals such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, saponins, and alkaloids contribute to the regulation of blood glucose through mechanisms including insulin sensitization, inhibition of carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes, and enhancement of pancreatic β -cell function. This review consolidates current evidence on the phytochemistry, pharmacology, and therapeutic potential of traditional vegetables in the management of diabetes, highlighting their role as safe, effective, and accessible natural antidiabetic candidates.

Keywords: Traditional vegetables; Diabetes mellitus; Antidiabetic; Phytochemicals; Pharmacological evidence; Functional food.

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INTRODUCTION

Over 500 million individuals globally are affected by Diabetes mellitus (DM) and contributes to morbidity and mortality due to cardiovascular, renal, and neuropathic complications [1]. Conventional antidiabetic medications, such as insulin, sulfonylureas, and metformin, although effective, are associated with side effects including hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal discomfort, and long-term organ toxicity. Now days there is growing interest in dietary interventions and plant-based therapies as safer alternatives [2].

People's interest in herbal remedies has grown over the past decade due to concerns about synthetic drugs' side effects, especially for long-term use in conditions like diabetes. Many synthetic drug like biguanide, α -glucosidase inhibitors, thiazolidinediones, glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), sulfonylurea and dopamine-2 agonists, dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP-4), and sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT 2) inhibitors have been existed in the Market. But they will cause side effects likes' allergy, cancer, hepatitis for long consumption. Many people are turning toward natural medicine because they are less toxic. In simple word, —Let food be your medicine, and medicine be your food. [3]

China has a rich history of developing natural medicines, notably through Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), which focuses on herbal remedies and holistic approaches. China approved many herbals as antidiabetes such as *Panax ginseng*, *Momodica charantia*, *Lagenaria siceraria*, and *Psidium guajava*. Some products show synergism activity. TCM products have shown effectiveness comparable to Western drugs in managing diabetes, with some studies suggesting a 1.2-fold impact. However, a major challenge is the lack of standardized guidelines for TCM use in diabetes patients. [4] Given this gap, reviewing selected herbs is crucial to understand their effects and potential combinations, paving the way for developing effective TCM-like products.

Traditional vegetables have been part of human diets for centuries and often possess medicinal properties. Also consist bioactive compounds such as polyphenols, flavonoids, and saponins, which are implicated in glucose regulation [5,6]. Integrating these vegetables into daily diets offers a culturally acceptable and sustainable approach to diabetes management. [7]

The goal is for these herbs to complement or potentially replace synthetic diabetes medications. This review will explore promising herbal options, examining their active compounds, efficacy, mechanisms, and safety, given their widespread traditional use for diabetes management. The aim of this review is highlights antidiabetic drug-like TCM.

CLASSIFICATION OF DIABETES MELLITUS

Diabetes can be classified as:

- **Type 1 Diabetes (T1DM):** Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) is characterized by the autoimmune destruction of pancreatic β -cells, leading to an absolute deficiency of insulin. This condition usually develops in any age, and requires insulin therapy for survival [8].
- **Type 2 Diabetes (T2DM):** Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM): More than 90% cases are accounted as diabetes mellitus. It is characterized by a combination of resistance of insulin

develop in peripheral tissues and progressive β -cell dysfunction, resulting in impaired insulin secretion and chronic hyperglycemia. It also develop due to lifestyle factors such as physical inactivity, obesity and genetic [9].

- **Gestational Diabetes: Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM)** refers to glucose intolerance that is first recognized during pregnancy. It occurs due to hormonal changes that impair insulin action and may increase the risk of complications for both the mother and the fetus. Although blood glucose levels often return to normal after delivery. During pregnancy Hyperglycemia may develop. [10].
- **Other Types: other specific types of diabetes** include less common forms such as monogenic diabetes, secondary diabetes and diabetes associated with diseases of the exocrine pancreas. These forms are relatively rare but important for accurate diagnosis and targeted management [11].

Figure No. 01: Classification of Diabetes Mellitus PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

The pathophysiology of diabetes mellitus is complex and involves a combination of metabolic and cellular disturbances primarily driven by chronic hyperglycemia. Persistently elevated blood glucose levels lead to excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), resulting in oxidative stress, which plays a key role in the progression of the disease. This oxidative stress activates multiple biochemical pathways, including the polyol pathway, protein kinase C pathway, and formation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), all of which contribute to cellular damage. In addition, hyperglycemia triggers chronic low-grade inflammation by increasing the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ and IL-6, which further impair insulin signaling.

A critical aspect of diabetes progression is the apoptosis (programmed cell death) of pancreatic β -cells, which reduces insulin secretion over time. This is particularly evident in both Type 1 diabetes, where autoimmune destruction is predominant, and Type 2 diabetes, where metabolic stress contributes to β -cell dysfunction. Simultaneously, insulin resistance in peripheral tissues such as skeletal muscle, liver, and adipose tissue reduces glucose uptake and utilization. The liver continues to produce glucose through gluconeogenesis despite high blood glucose levels, further aggravating hyperglycemia. Over time, these metabolic abnormalities lead to glucose intolerance and sustained elevation of blood glucose levels. Chronic hyperglycemia also causes damage to vital organs, including the cardiovascular system (leading to atherosclerosis and heart disease), kidneys (resulting in diabetic nephropathy), and nervous system (causing neuropathy),

thereby contributing to long-term complications of diabetes ^[12]. Chronic high blood glucose can damage cardiovascular, renal, and neural tissues.

CONVENTIONAL THERAPY LIMITATIONS

Conventional management of diabetes primarily involves pharmacological interventions, including insulin therapy and oral hypoglycemic agents such as metformin, sulfonylureas, thiazolidinediones, and DPP-4 inhibitors. While these treatments are effective in controlling blood glucose levels, they are associated with several limitations. One major concern is the development of drug resistance or reduced efficacy over time, particularly in patients with Type 2 diabetes, where progressive β -cell dysfunction diminishes the response to oral medications. Additionally, many antidiabetic drugs are associated with adverse effects, such as hypoglycemia (commonly seen with insulin and sulfonylureas), gastrointestinal disturbances (with metformin), weight gain, and cardiovascular risks.

Another significant limitation is the high cost of long-term therapy, especially for insulin and newer antidiabetic drugs, which can be a financial burden for patients, particularly in developing countries. Furthermore, conventional therapies often focus on glycemic control but may not adequately address underlying issues such as oxidative stress, inflammation, and metabolic imbalance. These drawbacks highlight the growing need for complementary and alternative approaches, including the use of plant-based therapies and functional foods. Traditional vegetables and phytochemical-rich diets offer a promising, cost-effective, and safer adjunct to conventional treatments, with the potential to target multiple pathways involved in diabetes management. ^[13]

TRADITIONAL VEGETABLES WITH ANTIDIABETIC POTENTIAL

Traditional vegetables have long been used in dietary and ethnomedicinal practices for the management of diabetes. Their therapeutic potential is attributed to the presence of diverse phytochemicals that act through multiple mechanisms such as antioxidant activity, enzyme inhibition, and enhancement of insulin function. Based on their botanical classification and edible parts, these vegetables can be categorized into leafy, fruit, and root/tuber vegetables.

A. LEAFY VEGETABLES

1. AMARANTHUS SPP.

Amaranth is a dicotyledonous plant that produces grain-like seeds; it is classified as a pseudocereal, belonging to the genus *Amaranthus*, family *Amaranthaceae*, and subfamily *Amaranthoideae*.

Figure No. 02: *Amaranthus Spp.*

- **Phytochemicals:** Flavonoids, phenolic acids, betacyanins, saponins ^[14]. The plant contains high levels of phenolic acids, flavonoids (e.g., anthocyanins), and carotenoids. Key isolated compounds improving glucose metabolism include -spinasterol and palmitic acid.
- **Mechanism:** Amaranthus extracts inhibit carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes (-amylase, -glucosidase), reduce glycation, and inhibit Dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV), a target related to insulin secretion. ^[15] α -glucosidase inhibition, β -cell protection, improved insulin sensitivity. *A. viridis* and *A. spinosus* reduce fasting blood glucose and improve pancreatic-cell function, acting similarly to metformin or glibenclamide ^[16]

The bioactive compounds in foods such as amaranth may serve as adjuvants in preventing and managing T2D with the primary goal of avoiding fatal complications such as CD. ^[17] In maintaining a healthy diet, it's crucial to include a diverse range of foods in appropriate proportions. This ensures that we obtain sufficient levels of nutrients and bioactive

compounds, which are essential for promoting positive health outcomes. Today, functional foods are gaining popularity in the food market, given the proven health benefits of their bioactive compounds. Although research to support the antidiabetic activity of amaranth is still scarce, current evidence is sufficient to prove its value and functional potential as an alternative diet-therapeutic proposal.

Although different *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies of the antidiabetic potential of bioactive amaranth compounds have already been conducted, clinical trials are necessary to validate and confirm these compounds' efficacy, bioavailability, and safety. ^[18]

2. MORINGA OLEIFERA

Using *M. oleifera* leaf powder alongside medication may help manage blood sugar levels in women with type 2 diabetes.

Figure No. 03: Moringa Oleifera

Phytochemicals: *Moringa oleifera* exhibits significant antidiabetic potential, primarily due to bioactive phytochemicals including quercetin-3-glucoside, rutin, kaempferol glycosides, chlorogenic acid, and isothiocyanates. [19].

Mechanism: *M. oleifera* shows promise in managing diabetes by reducing blood glucose, improving glucose tolerance, and boosting insulin sensitivity. primarily through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. [20] Enhances glucose uptake via AMPK activation, antioxidant activity. Moringa inhibits α -amylase and α -glucosidase activities, reducing the release of glucose into the bloodstream. Rich in phytochemicals like quercetin and chlorogenic acid, it aids in reducing hepatic lipid accumulation and managing type 2 diabetes by slowing glucose absorption and boosting glucose uptake in tissues [21]. It increases PPAR levels, enhancing insulin sensitivity, and reverses damaged pancreatic islet cells.

BRASSICA OLERACEA (CABBAGE, KAL E)

Figure No. 04: Brassica Oleracea

Phytochemicals: Glucosinolates (e.g., glucoraphanin, sinigrin), Isothiocyanates (e.g., sulforaphane – derived from glucosinolates), Flavonoids (quercetin, kaempferol), Phenolic acids (ferulic acid, caffeic acid), Vitamin C and carotenoids [22]. These phytochemicals work synergistically to improve metabolic health and reduce hyperglycemia

Mechanism: Antioxidant-mediated β -cell protection, modulation of carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes Oxidative stress is a major cause of pancreatic β -cell dysfunction in diabetes. The antioxidants present in *Brassica oleracea* neutralize free radicals, thereby protecting β -cells and maintaining insulin secretion. The plant extracts inhibit enzymes such as α -amylase and α -glucosidase, delaying carbohydrate digestion and reducing glucose absorption [23]. In vivo studies show improved postprandial glucose regulation. In vivo studies have demonstrated that consumption of *Brassica oleracea* leads to improved postprandial glucose regulation, indicating its effectiveness in controlling blood sugar spikes after meals. [24]. These findings support its inclusion as a functional food in diabetic diets.

B. FRUIT VEGETABLES

1. SOLANUM MELONGENA (EGGPLANT)

Figure No. 05: Solanum Melongena

Phytochemicals: chlorogenic acid, Nasunin (anthocyanin), Delphinidin derivatives, Flavonoids (quercetin, rutin), Phenolic acid [25].

Mechanism: The antidiabetic activity is mediated through multiple complementary mechanisms. Firstly, dual enzyme inhibition of α -amylase and α -glucosidase by chlorogenic acid and flavonoids plays a crucial role in controlling postprandial hyperglycemia by slowing the breakdown of carbohydrates and reducing glucose absorption in the intestine. In addition, these bioactive compounds modulate key enzymes involved in glucose metabolism by inhibiting

glucose-6-phosphatase, thereby suppressing hepatic gluconeogenesis, while simultaneously enhancing glycogen synthesis in the liver and muscle tissues, which promotes glucose storage.

Furthermore, strong antioxidant protection is provided by compounds such as nasunin, which effectively scavenges free radicals and protects lipid membranes as well as pancreatic β -cells from oxidative damage, thereby preserving insulin secretion. The improvement of insulin sensitivity is another important mechanism, where phytochemicals enhance insulin receptor activity and activate downstream signaling pathways, leading to increased glucose uptake by peripheral tissues. Lastly, these compounds exhibit a lipid-lowering effect by reducing levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and triglycerides, which helps in improving insulin resistance and overall metabolic health. [26] Diabetic rats exhibited improved glycemic control and lipid profiles [27].

2. CUCURBITA PEPO (PUMPKIN)

Figure No. 06: Cucurbita Pepo

Phytochemicals: Cucurbitacin, pectin, carotenoids (β -carotene, lutein), Polysaccharides (bioactive pumpkin polysaccharides), Flavonoids and phenolic compounds [28].

Mechanism: Insulinotropic activity, enhanced insulin sensitivity. The antidiabetic activity is mediated through multiple mechanisms. Pumpkin polysaccharides exhibit insulinotropic activity by stimulating the regeneration and functional activity of pancreatic β -cells, thereby increasing insulin secretion. In addition, these compounds enhance insulin sensitivity by improving insulin receptor function and associated signaling pathways, which leads to increased glucose uptake by peripheral tissues. The presence of pectin contributes to delayed carbohydrate absorption, as it forms a viscous gel in the intestine that slows glucose entry into the bloodstream and helps reduce postprandial spikes.

Furthermore, carotenoids and phenolic compounds provide antioxidant and cytoprotective effects by reducing oxidative stress and protecting pancreatic cells from damage. The regulation of lipid

metabolism is another important mechanism, as these bioactive compounds reduce lipid accumulation and improve overall metabolic balance, which is closely associated with reduced insulin resistance and better glycemic control. [29] Animal studies showed decreased fasting glucose and improved lipid metabolism [30].

3. MOMORDICA DIOICA

Figure No. 07: Cucurbita Pepo

Momordica dioica is a perennial, dioecious climbing plant belonging to the family Cucurbitaceae. It is widely consumed as a traditional vegetable in India and is commonly known as spiny gourd or kantola. The immature fruits are used as a vegetable and are valued for both nutritional and medicinal properties.

Phytochemicals: Flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, triterpenoids, glycosides, and phenolic compounds. The plant is rich in antioxidants and contains bioactive compounds that contribute to glucose regulation. Important constituents include momordicin-like compounds, sterols, and phenolic derivatives that play a role in antidiabetic activity.

Mechanism: The antidiabetic activity of *Momordica dioica* is mediated through multiple complementary mechanisms. Its bioactive phytoconstituents, including flavonoids, saponins, and phenolic compounds, inhibit key carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes such as α -amylase and α -glucosidase, thereby delaying the breakdown and absorption of glucose in the intestine. Additionally, the plant enhances insulin secretion by stimulating pancreatic β -cells and helps in protecting and possibly regenerating these cells from oxidative damage due to its strong antioxidant properties. It also improves peripheral insulin sensitivity, facilitating better glucose uptake by tissues. Furthermore, *Momordica dioica* reduces oxidative stress and glycation processes, both of which are closely linked to the progression of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Collectively, these actions contribute to lowering blood glucose levels and improving overall glycemic control.

C. ROOT AND TUBER VEGETABLES

1. DIOSCOREA SPP. (YAM)

Figure No. 08: Dioscorea Spp.

Phytochemicals: Diosgenin, saponins, Allantoin, Phenolic compounds, Dietary fibers [31].

Furthermore, inhibition of inflammatory pathways contributes to better metabolic control by suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokines, which are known to promote insulin resistance. Another important mechanism is the reduction of lipid peroxidation, which protects cellular membranes from oxidative damage and supports overall metabolic function, thereby contributing to improved glycemic regulation. Animal models of diabetes showed reduced blood glucose and lipid peroxidation [33]

2. IPOMOEA BATATAS (SWEET POTATO)

Figure No. 09: Ipomoea Batatas

Phytochemicals: Polyphenols, anthocyanins, Chlorogenic acid, dietary fiber, Carotenoids [34].

Mechanism: The antidiabetic effect is achieved through multiple coordinated mechanisms. Inhibition of α -glucosidase slows the digestion of carbohydrates, thereby reducing postprandial glucose levels. Additionally, polyphenols enhance insulin sensitivity by improving insulin receptor signaling and promoting efficient glucose uptake in peripheral tissues. These compounds also regulate glucose transporters by facilitating GLUT4 translocation to the cell membrane, which further enhances cellular glucose entry.

Moreover, anthocyanins exhibit strong antioxidant activity by reducing oxidative stress and protecting pancreatic β -cells from damage, thus supporting insulin secretion. The modulation of hepatic glucose metabolism is another important mechanism, where these bioactive compounds suppress gluconeogenesis while increasing glycogen storage in the liver, contributing to better overall glycemic control. [35] Clinical trials indicate improved postprandial glucose and insulin response [36].

PHYTOCHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS AND MECHANISMS

Phytochemicals are biologically active compounds derived from plants that play a key role managing diabetes mellitus. Their antidiabetic activity is mediated through multiple mechanisms such as increase insulin secretion, improve insulin sensitivity, inhibition of carbohydrate digestion, reducing glucose absorption, and protecting pancreatic β -cells. Among these, flavonoids, phenolic acids, saponins, and alkaloids are the most significant classes contributing to glycemic control.

1. FLAVONOIDS

Enhance GLUT4-mediated glucose uptake. Flavonoids increase the translocation of GLUT4 transporters to the cell membrane in skeletal muscle and adipose tissue. This enhances cellular glucose uptake and lowers blood glucose levels, mimicking insulin action. [37] Protect β -cells from oxidative stress-induced apoptosis. In diabetes, oxidative stress damages β -cells, reducing insulin secretion. Flavonoids protect these cells by reducing oxidative stress, thereby preserving insulin-producing capacity. [38] Flavonoids enhance insulin receptor signaling pathways, leading to improved glucose utilization and reduced insulin resistance. They inhibit enzymes such as α -amylase and α -glucosidase, delaying carbohydrate digestion and reducing postprandial hyperglycemia.

Examples: quercetin, kaempferol [39].

2. PHENOLIC ACIDS

Phenolic acids are important plant metabolites known for their role in regulating glucose metabolism and controlling hyperglycemia. Phenolic acids inhibit α -glucosidase and α -amylase

enzymes, thereby slowing glucose release into the bloodstream after meals. They decrease intestinal glucose absorption, contributing to lower postprandial glucose levels. Phenolic acids increase insulin signaling pathways and improve glucose uptake in peripheral tissues. These compounds suppress gluconeogenesis in the liver, reducing endogenous glucose production. Act as antioxidants and inhibit carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes. Phenolic acids neutralize free radicals and reduce oxidative stress, which is responsible the development of insulin resistance and diabetic complications such as neuropathy and nephropathy. ^[40]

Examples: chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid ^[41]

3. SAPONINS

Saponins are glycosidic compounds that contribute significantly to glucose regulation and metabolic balance. Improve insulin sensitivity and modulate lipid metabolism. Saponins enhance the responsiveness of body cells to insulin, thereby facilitating efficient glucose uptake. Some saponins stimulate pancreatic β -cells, leading to increased insulin release. By influencing glucose metabolism pathways, saponins help in maintaining normal blood glucose levels. Saponins may slow down intestinal glucose absorption, contributing to better glycemic control. ^[42]

Examples: diosgenin ^[43].

4. ALKALOIDS

Alkaloids are nitrogen-containing compounds with potent pharmacological effects, including significant antidiabetic activity. Enhance insulin secretion and protect against complications. Alkaloids stimulate pancreatic β -cells, leading to increased insulin production and improved glycemic control. They enhance peripheral glucose uptake and utilization, thereby lowering blood glucose levels. By controlling blood glucose levels, alkaloids indirectly help in preventing long-term complications of diabetes. ^[44]

Examples: solasodine ^[45].

CONCLUSION

Traditional vegetables offer a promising source of natural antidiabetic agents due to their rich phytochemical composition. Evidence from preclinical and clinical studies supports their unification into dietary strategies for managing diabetes. Traditional vegetables are contain bioactive phytochemicals like saponins, flavonoids, phenolic acids and alkaloids, which exhibit significant antidiabetic activity through multiple mechanisms including enzyme inhibition, improved insulin sensitivity, enhanced insulin secretion, and antioxidant protection of β -cells. Evidence from in vitro, in vivo, and clinical studies supports their role in lowering blood glucose levels and improving metabolic health. Due to their safety, affordability, and accessibility, these vegetables can serve as effective complementary approaches in diabetes management. However, further clinical studies and standardization is needed to fully establish their therapeutic potential

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